

Neutronic Advanced simulations with ODYSSEE, the new EDF and Framatome nuclear code system: application on EPR Design

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ABSTRACT

The paper presents high-fidelity transport calculation schemes, based on SP_N and S_N , which has been implemented in ODYSSEE, the new EDF and Framatome nuclear code system. These schemes aim to support the industrial ODYSSEE computational chain which relies on a diffusion solver. They enable performing precise neutronics simulations, with thermal-hydraulics and fuel thermal-mechanics feedbacks and fuel depletion, to support the validation of the industrial ODYSSEE chain. Directly integrated inside the platform for ease of use by engineers, these neutronic advanced solutions are also used to develop new models, which could be used in the future to improve the precision of the industrial tool. The validation process of the SP_N and S_N schemes is based, in part, on comparisons with Monte-Carlo simulations. In this paper, SP_3 and S_8 results are compared to TRIPOLI-4[®] simulations on a 3D EPR core benchmark. Both schemes show strong agreement in terms of reactivity and fission rates prediction at both assembly and pin-wise level. The precision of these schemes illustrated in this paper is considered very encouraging. Further validation work is underway to demonstrate these schemes' capabilities to serve as a reference across the entire reactor operating domain.

Keywords: SPN solver, SN solver, EPR, 3D core simulation, validation, neutronic

1. INTRODUCTION

Verification and Validation (V&V), required for qualified and accurate computational tools, relies on comparisons between simulations and representative physical quantities within a given domain of applicability. In neutronic core simulation, more precisely in ODYSSEE, representative physical quantities mainly come from experimental measurements in EDF PWR reactors and Monte Carlo transport simulations (more details in [1]). On one hand, experimental measurements expose a limited range of neutronic physical quantities in real-world industrial conditions. On the other hand, Monte Carlo transport simulations offer access to full ranges of neutronic physical quantities in very specific conditions (static conditions, mainly with isothermal and undepleted materials) at very high computational cost.

To address the inherent limitations of experimental measurements and Monte Carlo methods, research conducted at EDF and Framatome has led to the development of deterministic neutronic advanced schemes for solving the Boltzmann transport equation, specifically tailored for PWR applications. These high-fidelity schemes aim to cover the full domain of use of the industrial ODYSSEE [2] and enable detailed neutronic analysis to support code validation and the development of physical models.

The key components of the high-fidelity schemes involve two neutronic solvers implemented in COCAGNE, the 3D full-core simulation platform for PWRs in ODYSSEE:

- a neutron transport S_N solver based on the discrete ordinates method [3].
- a simplified neutron transport P_N (SP_N) solver [4].

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One of the main advantages of these neutronic advanced schemes is their direct implementation in COCAGNE. Supported by an efficient Python interface, engineers are able to quickly switch from industrial simulations to these advanced methodologies.

This paper presents these high-fidelity schemes in ODYSSEE, the new EDF and Framatome nuclear code system, from first step lattice calculation, in Section 2, to 3D core simulation in Section 3. In Section 4, a numerical benchmark on a simplified EPR design is performed to illustrate their capabilities.

2. Multi-parametric Neutronic Libraries Generator - CARABAS

In two-step methodology, lattice simulations produce neutronic properties later used in core simulations. Within the ODYSSEE platform, this role is fulfilled by CARABAS, a multi-parametric neutronic libraries generator based on the APOLLO2 (version 2.8) physical modules developed by the French Atomic Energy Commission (CEA) [5]. CARABAS also uses the CEA v5.2.0 nuclear data library mainly based on JEFF-3.1.1 evaluations [6] with the SHEM 281-group energy mesh [7]. COCAGNE high-fidelity schemes require neutron libraries for both fuel and reflectors regions, hereafter explained.

2.1. Fuel Assembly Libraries

The generation of fuel assembly libraries in CARABAS is based on the same lattice calculations as those used in the industrial scheme (described in detail in [2] and summarized below). In CARABAS, APOLLO2 solves the multi-group neutron transport equation on 2D fuel assembly geometries. In comparison with the industrial scheme, differences only arise during the transport multi-group cross-section homogenization, where a cell-by-cell mesh and an 8-group energy mesh are generally adopted in the high-fidelity schemes. The energy boundaries of the 8-group mesh were optimized through error minimization between SP_N and TRIPOLI-4[®] simulations on a few representative configurations. More refined energy meshes can be employed for specific purposes, resulting in additional computational costs at core level. Scattering cross sections are modeled using Legendre polynomials expansion with the P0 and P1 moments stored in the multi-parametric libraries.

Figure 1 summarizes the main steps adopted by CARABAS to produce neutronic properties for each feedback parameters set:

- (1) Using self-shielded cross-sections, the Boltzmann equation is solved in two steps: first, the flux is calculated with Collision Probability (P_{ij}) solver on a spatially simplified mesh with fine energy structure (281 energy groups) and is then used to homogenize cross-sections on a coarser energy mesh (36 energy groups). The homogenized cross-sections are secondly used by APOLLO2's Method of Characteristics (MOC) solver to compute the flux on a refined geometry.
- (2) Using a flux reconstructed from the two previous steps, cross-sections (XS) are homogenized on the desired spatial and energy structure, defined by core-level schemes.

An additional step is done when fuel isotopic depletion is considered and consists of solving Bateman equation for an extended isotope chain containing about 170 nuclides.

A SPH equivalence [8] with flux-volume normalization is then performed with the core-solver on each fuel assembly using symmetric boundaries conditions for consistency with APOLLO2 heterogeneous transport.

2.1. Radial Reflector Assembly Libraries

In 2016, EDF presented a benchmark for radial reflector model for neutronic advanced simulation [9]. This work showed good agreement with the 2D explicit-reflector model but focused on the 1D radial-reflector model which was considered more time-efficient and easier to set up for users. Since 2018, EDF and Framatome have investigated the possibility to industrialize a 2D reflector model: an efficient lattice calculation scheme inspired by ODYSSEE lattice/fuel scheme has been developed, enabling for an explicit geometrical description of the reflector at limited computational cost. This method is presented in Subsection 2.2.2. These developments have been integrated in CARABAS which now computes the neutronic properties for radial reflector based on the 2D explicit-reflector model [10].

Within the high-fidelity framework, 2D explicit-reflector is used in COCAGNE 3D core simulation. It also allows producing 2D deterministic reference solution, used for neutronic validation [1].

Figure 1. Overview of fuel assembly library generation by CARABAS.
 (1) 2D transport resolution with APOLLO2 solvers,
 (2) XS space-energy homogenization (core scheme-dependent).

2.1.1. User interface

CARABAS presents an API designed to meet engineer's requirements. The generation of reflector libraries using a 2D explicit-reflector model [10] is extremely simplified by CARABAS which automatically constructs complex geometries from a minimal set of input data. For example, Figure 2 illustrates the geometry and material description for the Watts Bar 1 benchmark [11], generated by CARABAS using approximately twenty variables defining the radial reflector. The encapsulation of such complex geometry generation, as well as complex calculation schemes, is important to ensure simulation robustness and reproducibility.

Figure 2. Example of geometry and material description for 2D lattice simulation in CARABAS.

2.1.2. 2D explicit-reflector model

The space-energy distribution of the neutron flux within the reflector is determined by simulating one-eighth of a two-dimensional core slice using the APOLLO2 code. The simulation scheme follows the ODYSSEE methodology (two-step simulation presented in Subsection 2.1) and incorporates dedicated MOC options. These adaptations aim to capture the anisotropy of the neutron flux, notably with P3 expansion order for scattering cross-sections, while optimizing computational constraints related to

memory usage. Homogenization of the reflector materials' cross-sections is then performed adopting the same energy group structure as the core-level computation: pin-wise and 8 energy groups meshes.

2.2. Axial Reflectors Assembly Libraries

A 1D reflector model is employed to characterize both the upper and lower reflectors. In this model, the space-energy distribution of the neutron flux within the reflector is determined by simulating a one-dimensional slab, composed of homogeneous layers, with APOLLO2 S_{16} solver and 281 groups energy mesh with P3 expansion order for scattering cross-sections. The dimensions and material compositions of each homogeneous layer closely approximate the reactor's technological geometry and material specifications. Subsequently, flux-weighted homogenization of the reflector materials' cross-sections are performed for each layer, adopting the same energy group structure as the core-level computation: pin-wise and 8 energy groups meshes.

3. Neutronic Advanced simulation with COCAGNE platform

COCAGNE is a 3D full-core simulation platform designed for PWR (see detailed description in [2, 12]). COCAGNE implemented two neutronic solvers that both operate on Cartesian geometries:

- a Simplified P_N (SP_N) [4] solver, using a Raviart-Thomas finite element method (RTk).
- a discrete ordinates (S_N) solver [3], with a Diamond Difference spatial scheme, consistent with the SP_N which is used for Diffusion Synthetic Acceleration (DSA) [13].

Within the high-fidelity framework, the SP_N solver is employed with third-order approximation (SP_3), first-order finite elements for radial discretization (RT1) and second-order finite elements for axial discretization (RT2). This solver is applied to solve the simplified transport equation, using a pin-wise radial representation and 8-group energy mesh. The axial discretization is case-specific and is tailored to the technological characteristics of the reactor core. Furthermore, in the ODYSSEE industrial calculation scheme, the SP_N solver (at first order with a diffusion correction term) is employed to solve the two-group diffusion equation [2] and has benefited from extensive optimization efforts over several years, resulting in significant reductions in computational time.

The S_N solver is specifically designed for high-fidelity simulations employing a zero-order Diamond Difference spatial scheme (DD0). It solves the transport equation with the same axial mesh and energy group structure as the SP_3 solver. To ensure numerical stability and accurately capture flux heterogeneities, particularly at assembly and fuel-reflector interfaces, a refined radial mesh is required. In practice, each radial pin-wise cell is further subdivided into two parts along both the x and y directions, which significantly increases memory requirements. Each mono-group iteration is accelerated with DSA (SP_1 RT0). Currently, this solver is primarily used for Research and Development (R&D) activities and remains under active development, with ongoing efforts focused on improving its performance and stability.

4. Numerical Benchmark on a Simplified EPR Design

The COCAGNE high-fidelity schemes have been tested on a numerical benchmark to demonstrate their capabilities to be used as an industrial reference tool.

For this purpose, a hypothetical design of the EPR was selected to benchmark these deterministic calculations against a stochastic reference. A primary simplification involved the removal of assembly spacer grids and in-core instrumentations. This benchmark was considered as an opportunity to highlight the ability to model an EPR first core with a high level of fidelity. The latter is characterized by a heavy reflector composed of stainless-steel impacting significantly the flux spectrum near the fuel-reflector interface.

For this exercise, the EPR core is modeled under simplified Beginning of Cycle (BOC) conditions at Hot Zero Power (HZP) with All Rods Out (ARO). Fuel and moderator temperatures (574 K) were chosen to allow the use of pre-tabulated nuclear data for Monte Carlo simulation, thereby avoiding any interpolation approximations.

The deterministic results will be validated through comparison with Monte Carlo reference for several physical quantities: the effective multiplication factor (k_{eff}), 2D radial map of assembly fission rates and 2D radial map of cell fission rates. k_{eff} comparisons aims to validate the global simulation of neutron reaction within the system, while the other comparisons focus on the 2D spatial distribution of neutron flux. Fission rates were chosen, rather than power distribution, to avoid potential biases associated with the power deposition model adopted by the different codes.

Statistical error on integrated fission rates (in %)

Normalized integrated fission rates

Figure 3. TRIPOLI-4[®] statistical uncertainties of EPR benchmark fission rates and associated normalized values for the assembly score (a)-(b) and the pin-by-pin score (c)-(d)

4.1. Monte Carlo reference simulations

This EPR benchmark was simulated using TRIPOLI-4.12[®] [14, 15] to perform reference simulations. TRIPOLI-4[®] is the fourth generation of the 3D continuous-energy Monte-Carlo code developed at CEA. TRIPOLI-4.12[®] was used with the CEAV5.2.0 nuclear data library, mainly based on JEFF-3.1.1 evaluations [6]. The full 3D geometry of the core was generated using the ROOT package [16].

The fission reaction rates were integrated over the active height of the core, and the results were calculated for both the assembly and pin-wise meshes.

Simulations were run on EDF's cluster GAIA, using 8 nodes with 32 processors on each (Intel® Xeon® Gold 6140 Processor, 192Go of RAM), for 3 days. 4420 batches of 10^5 neutrons regrouped with a packet length of 200 batches were simulated, after an initial discard of 300 batches on each processor to ensure an initial convergence of the source.

Since the whole core geometry was simulated, spatial convergence of the fission rates scores were controlled to ensure the symmetry of the results obtained. Indeed, due to clustering of neutrons, the different scores are not by nature symmetrical and convergence inside their statistical errors should be assured. As shown in *Figure 3*, results are well enough converged for both meshes. A post-processing step is used to rebuild symmetry. For each position in the core, the score is replaced by the mean score value from all of its symmetrical positions. In terms of k_{eff} , the standard deviation reached is less than 1 pcm as reported in *Table I*.

4.2. Neutronic Advanced simulations and comparisons

The EPR benchmark was simulated using COCAGNE with both SP_3 and S_8 solvers.

The effective multiplication factors are presented in *Table I*. The results demonstrate good agreement between COCAGNE and TRIPOLI-4® with reactivity underestimated by less than 20 pcm.

Table I. Effective multiplication factor

TRIPOLI-4®	SP_3	S_8
$1.00099 \pm 1 \text{ pcm}$	1.00081	1.00089

Figure 4 (a) and (b) illustrates the comparisons of 2D axially integrated fission rates at the assembly level. Both the SP_3 and S_8 solvers, with a 2D explicit radial reflector model, show low discrepancies compared to TRIPOLI-4®, with Root Mean Square (RMS) values of 0.5% and 0.8%, respectively. However, both COCAGNE simulations reveal an underestimation of fission rate for core-center assemblies (minimum -1.2% for SP_3 and -1.7% for S_8) and an overestimation of fission rate for assemblies along the core diagonal periphery (maximum +0.9% for SP_3 and +1.2% for S_8). The superior accuracy of SP_3 compared to S_8 DD0 suggests potential limitations of the DD0 spatial description and highlights the need for more refined flux spatial approximations (e.g., DD1).

Further examination of the 2D pin-wise axially integrated fission rates in Figure 4 (c) and (d) shows that while the minimum and maximum errors remain low, they clearly reflect the diagonal center-periphery imbalance effects previously observed.

Despite these localized effects, the overall accuracy of both SP_3 and S_8 results is considered very good, with pin-wise RMS errors of 0.6% and 0.8%, respectively.

These results are given as an illustration of the validation of SP_3 and S_8 schemes. First results are very encouraging and further works (especially comparisons against experimental data) are underway to demonstrate that SP_3 scheme can be used as a reference across the entire reactor functional domain (with thermal-hydraulics and fuel thermal-mechanics feedbacks and fuel depletion).

While the precision of the S_8 scheme is sufficient for use as a reference, its high computational cost (more than ten times higher than with the SP_3 scheme) and memory occupation **limit its practical application** in favor of the SP_3 scheme.

Figure 4. 2D fission rates comparison against TRIPOLI-4[®] reference : at assembly level for (a) SP₃ and for (b) S₈ and at pin-wise level for (c) SP₃ and (d) S₈.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has introduced high-fidelity schemes developed by EDF and Framatome and implemented within the industrial PWR core computational platform ODYSSEE. These solutions, based on SP_N and S_N neutronics solvers, aim to support the industrial ODYSSEE computational chain by enabling accurate neutronics static and depletion simulations with thermal-hydraulic and fuel-thermic feedback. Their validation has been illustrated with comparisons against TRIPOLI-4[®] simulations, and both SP₃ and S₈ schemes have demonstrated strong agreement in reactivity predictions and radial fission rate distributions. Before being considered as a reference, capable of providing 3D evaluations across the entire reactor functional domain, further validation work is required and ongoing.

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